

IMPACT ANALYSIS OF MGNREGA ON WOMEN EMPOWERMENT IN RAJASTHAN

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ABSTRACT

A major section in world is facing problem of poverty and unemployment. Rural people specifically women are the victims of this poverty and unemployment, in order to eliminate these, government also undertake some employment and poverty alleviation programmes like MGNREGA.

Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) is first ever law internationally, that guarantees wage employment at an unprecedented scale. The primary objective of the MGNREGA is augmenting wage employment. Its auxiliary objective is strengthening natural resource management through works that address causes of chronic poverty like deforestation, drought and soil erosion and so encourage sustainable development.

To strengthen the democratic system and enhance transparency and accountability in it, the process outcomes are focused towards improving the grassroots methodology of democracy.

This paper discuss benefits of MGNREGA and its implementation, it focus to identify the influence and role of MGNREGA in rural women development and growth, and also suggested for the better implementation of this scheme. Mainly on the basis of primary data analysis, this paper attempts to highlight the role of MGNREGA in the empowerment of women in Rajasthan.

The current research study will forth valuable insights with respect to the implementation of the Act and would indubitably function as an eye-opener for the authorities and policy makers to recognize and remedy the problems and constraints in the implementation.

KEYWORDS: MGNREGA, Poverty, Rajasthan, Women Empowerment

1. INTRODUCTION

Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) is the flagship programme of the Government to influence the life of poor masses positively and enhance their development. MGNREGA aims at enhancing livelihood security of households in rural areas of the country by providing at least one hundred days of guaranteed wage employment in a financial year to every household whose adult members volunteer to do unskilled manual work.

SPECIFIC GOALS OF MAHATMA GANDHI NREGA

- To provide backup or alternative source of employment to the vulnerable groups of society so that they are strong and secure, both socially and economically.
- To create durable assets and strengthen the livelihood resource base of the rural poor.
- Flood management and drought-proofing in rural India.
- To act as a growth engine for sustainable development of an agricultural economy.
- Empowerment of the socially disadvantaged, especially women, Scheduled Tribes (STs) and Scheduled Castes (SCs) through the processes of a rights based legislation.
- Deepening democracy at the grass-roots by strengthening Panchayati Raj Institutions.

- Effecting greater accountability and transparency in governance.
- To eliminate or at least reduce practice of forced migration from rural to urban areas.
- In view of the above advantages, MGNREGA is much more than being simply an initiative of welfare. It is a constructive effort and a stepping stone for the development of Indian Economy.

Therefore Mahatma Gandhi NREGA has 3 distinct goals:

- *Promotive*
- *Protective*
- *Preventive*

It protects the rural poor from vulnerabilities by providing them demand based employment. It prevents risk associated with agricultural investment and forced migration of rural poor people. By increasing the demand of consumers, it indirectly promotes and enhances prosperity in the economy of rural areas.

Therefore Mahatma Gandhi NREGA is an influential instrument for ensuring inclusive growth in rural India through its impact on livelihood security, social protection and democratic empowerment.

MGNREGA addresses mainly to rural poor and their fundamental right to work and dignity. It also empowers local citizens to play an active role in the implementation of employment guarantee schemes through GRAMA SABHA, social audit, participatory planning and other means. It is considered to be a land mark in the history of poverty reduction strategies in India. This scheme intend to provide

employment to the rural poor during lean agricultural season and aims to create village asset and bring sustainable development, further, the attempt is to provide adequate employment to women at equal wage .the program therefore requires 2/3 of all workers are women.

So many studies reveal that MGNREGA was implemented for the growth and development of rural area by ensuring 100 days of employment. The main objective of this study is to evaluate and understand the impact of MGNREG in socio-economic development and women empowerment in Rajasthan.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

A number of literature based on empirical studies are available on the role of MGNREGA in achieving livelihood security and promoting sustainable development. These studies depicts that MGNREGA programmes has shown mixed result so far in whole India.

Narayana Sudha (2008) wrote an article based on the social audit survey findings on creche facilities and childcare practices under NREGA in Villupuram district of Tamil Nadu. It elaborates the difficult predicaments of young mothers who worked under the NREGA and provides ample evidences of urgent need for childcare facility at all worksites. A number of women mentioned that because of the problem of childcare they were often not able to join the NREGA worksites at all, critical as this was for the economic well-being of the family, especially for those who are landless and illiterate.

Mehrotra Santosh (2008) this paper examines the performance of the National Rural Employment Guarantee Programme since its launch in August 2005. It provides a summary of progress in certain areas and also highlights specific weaknesses. Finally, it describes the challenges that lie ahead and suggests how these can be overcome.

Dreze Jean et al. (2008) explained that the draft CAG report on NREGA does not present sufficient proof of misappropriation of funds nor does it certifies NREGA to be a failure. The methodology of muster roll verification was developed in Rajasthan in the context of the right to information movement.

Roy Aruna and Dey Nikhil (2009) revealed that the NREGA evolved out of a political response to a people's movement and the articulated needs of rural workers. It put the people to seek work in a legal framework and approached development through the economic and social empowerment of the poor and the marginalised. The assets created should benefit the poorest and most marginalised communities first.

3.OBJECTIVE OF CURRENT STUDY

- ❖ To evaluate the impact of MGNREGA on socio economic development & women empowerment
- ❖ To analyze the implementation process
- ❖ To understand how panchayath implement this programme under the act 2005

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- **Sources of Data:** The study is exploratory in nature and is based on both primary and secondary data.
- **Secondary data** was has been collected with the help of Books, Magazines, Newspapers, Research Articles, Research Journals, E-Journals, RBI Report, Report of NABARD etc.
- **Primary data** was enumerated from a field survey in the study region. (Rajasthan).
- **Area of Sampling:** The study was conducted in the district of Jaipur and Ajmer of Rajasthan through a field survey to get an insight of the benefits and challenges faced by women under MGNREGA.
- **Sample Size:** 200 samples from 5 from the area of study have been considered to conduct the present study.
- **Method for data collection:** A structured interview schedule was

prepared and used for collecting data from the women MGNREGA member. Both open ended and close ended questions were included in the schedule.

- **Hypothesis to be analyzed: H_0 :** There is no difference in mean income of respondents before and after MGNREGA which directly leads to women empowerment.
- **Statistical tools:** Simple correlation coefficient, paired t-test, cross tabulation and percentage analysis are used for the analysis of the data.

5. OUTCOME AND ANALYSIS

In current research study 100 women members were analyzed from Jaipur and Ajmer region of Rajasthan. Demographic details of respondents were as depicted:

(a). Age of Respondents:

TABLE 1 AGE GROUP OF WOMEN RESPONDENTS

Age	AJMER		JAIPUR	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Below 18	12	12%	6	6%
19-25	8	8%	10	10%
26-30	10	10%	18	18%
31-35	15	15%	12	12%
36-45	39	39%	35	35%
46-55	11	11%	15	15%

55 & Above	5	5%	4	4%
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CHART 1 AGE GROUP OF WOMEN RESPONDENTS

The above table evaluates the age of respondents for the current study. In Ajmer the maximum respondents 39% were from the age group of 36 to 45 years and similarly in Jaipur the maximum 35% respondents were in the category of 36 to 45 years of age group. The minimum respondents 5% and 4% for both the districts were above the age of 55. There were only 12% from Ajmer and 6% from Jaipur who were below 18 years of

age whereas 15% and 12% from both the districts had respondents from 31 to 35 years of age. The remaining 8% and 10% were between 19-25 years of age whereas 11% and 15% were between 46 to 55 years of age. It can be concluded from the table that maximum respondents from both the districts had middle aged or above aged women as compared to young ones.

(b) Education of Women Respondents :

TABLE 2 EDUCATION OF WOMEN RESPONDENTS

Education	AJMER		JAIPUR	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Illiterate	41	41%	28	28%
Primary	35	35%	43	43%
10th	17	17%	9	9%
12th	5	5%	13	13%
Degree	2	2%	7	7%

CHART 2 EDUCATION OF WOMEN RESPONDENTS

In the above table the next parameter was education level of respondents where maximum respondents 41% from Ajmer were illiterate whereas in Jaipur 28% completed their studies till primary level. The minimum respondents 2% and 7% for both the districts were having a degree. Jaipur had 43% of illiterate whereas Ajmer had 35% respondents who were educated till primary. The remaining 17% from Ajmer and 9% from Jaipur were 10th pass whereas 5% and 13% from both the districts were

12th pass. It can be analyzed from the above table that most of the women from villages of Ajmer and Jaipur were either illiterate or were having education till primary.

IMPACT OF MGNREGA ON WOMEN EMPOWERMENT DATA ANALYSIS

Few statements were analyzed to elucidate the impact of MGNREGA on women empowerment which are depicted below:

(a) Did you find benefits in your savings from MGNREGA?

TABLE 3 BENEFITS N SAVINGS FROM MGNREGA

Respondent's Opinion	AJMER		JAIPUR	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	63	63%	57	57%
No	37	37%	43	43%

The above table analyses the responses of respondents whether they find benefits in their savings from MGNREGA support for their loan purpose or not in which maximum respondents 63% from Ajmer and 57% respondents from Jaipur found benefits in

their savings from MGNREGA support for their loan purpose whereas only 37% and 43% respondents didn't find any benefits from their savings from MGNREGA support for their loan purposes.

(b) Your Monthly income after MGNREGA.

TABLE 4 IMPACTS IN MONTHLY INCOME AFTER MGNREGA

Monthly income after availing MGNREGA	AJMER		JAIPUR	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Highly increased	18	18%	21	21%
increased	32	32%	34	34%
Neither increase nor decrease	25	25%	29	29%
decreased	20	20%	11	11%
Highly decreased	5	5%	5	5%

From the above table the monthly income has been examined after availing MGNREGA. Maximum respondents 32% and 34% from Ajmer and Jaipur agreed that their income increased after availing MGNREGA whereas minimum respondents 5% from Ajmer and 5% from Jaipur believe that their income has highly decreased after availing MGNREGA. There were 18% and 21% respondents who believe that their income has highly increased after availing MGNREGA whereas 25% and 29% respondents from both districts were also there who feel that there is neither an increase nor decrease in their income after MGNREGA. The remaining 20% and 11% respondents believe that their income has

decreased after MGNREGA. It can be concluded that many income of many respondents had increased due to MGNREGA

HYPOTHESIS TESTING

To analyze the hypothesis (H_0 : There is no difference in mean income of respondents before and after MGNREGA which directly leads to women empowerment) on mean scores of above table following Leven's T Test was used and results are depicted as below:

Independent Samples Test										
VARIABLE		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Woman Empowerment	JAIPUR	.648	.422	7.426	148	.000	0.59	0.08	0.43	0.75
	AJMER	1.453	.230	4.062	155	.000	0.34	0.08	0.18	0.51

In the study of Woman Empowerment as an important variable of current research it was found that at 148 degree of freedom t value was 7.426 and 4.062 for Jaipur and Ajmer respondents separately Significance value was obtained at 0.00, which is significant in both cases.

Above hypotheses testing interoperates that as the 2 tailed value for Ajmer and Jaipur seems to be significant in above variable (Women Empowerment),thus it can be postulated that **Null Hypotheses H_0** : There is no difference in mean income of respondents before and after MGNREGA which directly leads to women empowerment is **Rejected and alternate hypothesis H_1** : There is a significant difference in mean income of respondents before and after MGNREGA which directly leads to women empowerment is **accepted and proved**

5. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Presently, the MGNREGA is being implemented in the all rural districts of the country. MGNREGA has resulted into major financial inclusion where in bank/post office accounts have been opened for the families getting employment. Ministry has advised all the states to ensure payment of wages fully through the accounts.

- ❖ The study reveals that,95% of participants are women workers
- ❖ The implementation process undertaken by panchayath are correct and within time bound
- ❖ This scheme enhance social skills like communication, mobility, participation, decision making among women who participated in this scheme
- ❖ From this study, it is clear that most of the workers have any one of the savings like RD, insurance, saving a/c etc. This will enable for the economic development.

- ❖ MGNREGA is an Act that aims to strengthen the women employment by enforcing that about 33 percent of total work force should be women and also that there will be equal wages for men and women. It is playing a substantial role in creating employment for women there by, leading to greater independence and self respect among women.

The present paper has made an attempt to study the impact of MGNREGA on socio-economic development and women empowerment. Women worker feels highly satisfied with the MNREGA employment as now they get the wages equal to the male workers and also she can participate in the up liftment of her family by becoming an earning member of the family thus, MNREGA has brought economic independence among women, which was the main aim of MNREGA. It is programme that has affected the lives of rural women in real sense.

It is the most significant act in the history of Indian polity in many ways like grass-root level participation of every citizen and beneficiary through democratic process, multi-layered social audit and transparency mechanism by involvement of civil society, comprehensive planning at village level towards sustainable and equitable development etc. Important salient feature of the Act is to improve the quality of life of rural households who are vulnerable to out-migration in search of daily wage employment by channelizing the wage workforce towards developmental activities at the village level itself.

Though different studies conducted at various levels show different conclusions, it can be acknowledged from the present study that despite of bottlenecks, MGNREGA is capable of helping the poor to upscale themselves to a better living and playing a significantly positive role in upgrading women empowerment.

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